

Total Asset Turnover (TATO) on Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Library Research

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Abstract - This study aims to determine the research mapping regarding the Total Asset Turnover (TATO) ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking using a mix-method approach, namely the VOSviewer bibliometric study and Library Research. Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping the distribution of journal publications around the TATO ratio; (2) mapping the results of the VOSviewer bibliometric visualization around the TATO ratio based on the number of clusters and their items; and (3) mapping research topics around the TATO ratio using a Library Research study. The results showed that: (1) based on the distribution of journal publications, there were 339 journal publications regarding the TATO ratio; (2) based on the mapping of the VOSviewer bibliometric study, the network visualization results around the TATO ratio are divided into 5 clusters and 104 topic items; (3) based on the mapping of Library Research studies, there are 26 topics around the influence of the TATO ratio. The implications and contributions of this research are to map research topics around TATO ratios in Islamic and Conventional Banking which are often or rarely researched by researchers so that they can be a reference for subsequent researchers.

Keywords: Total Asset Turnover (TATO); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic and Conventional Banking

I. INTRODUCTION

Total Asset Turnover Ratio (TATO) is an important financial ratio in measuring the efficiency of using company assets in generating income. Basically, the TATO ratio can help estimate how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate income. In the banking context, the TATO ratio can also help in evaluating

a bank's financial performance. The use of the TATO ratio in banking has grown along with the development of the financial industry. Initially, the TATO ratio was used generally to estimate the effectiveness of empowering bank assets in generating income. However, along with technological advances and increasingly fierce competition, the use of the TATO ratio is increasingly sharpened and made more specific (Aprisilya Wisnu, 2016).

One example of a more specific use of the TATO ratio is in measuring the effectiveness of asset use in supporting a bank's credit business. In this case, the TATO ratio can help banks understand how efficiently they use assets in providing credit to customers. Banks can use this ratio to improve their credit strategies and minimize unwanted credit risks. Apart from that, the TATO ratio is also used in evaluating bank performance in managing its investment portfolio. Banks can use this ratio to understand how effectively assets are used in generating income from investments. This ratio can also help banks make wiser investment decisions and optimize asset use in the long term. However, the use of the TATO ratio also has several disadvantages. First, the TATO ratio cannot differentiate between efficient and inefficient use of assets. Second, this ratio cannot measure the effectiveness of asset use over a long period of time. So, the use of the TATO ratio is always considered in a broader context to obtain an accurate perception of bank performance. Overall, the TATO ratio has evolved and is increasingly important in evaluating a bank's financial performance. However, it should be remembered that the use of the TATO ratio must always be considered in a broader context and used together with other financial ratios to obtain a comprehensive perception of banking performance (Nurdin, 2023) .

In the banking sector, the TATO ratio is also often used to evaluate bank financial performance. Therefore, research on the TATO ratio in banks always grows along with the development of the financial industry. First, research that measures the efficiency of using bank assets in generating income and evaluates things that impact the TATO ratio in banks in Lebanon. The research results show that the TATO ratio of banks in Lebanon tends to be stable, however there are several banks that have succeeded in increasing their TATO ratio through optimizing the use of their assets (Damayanti, 2020) . Second, research was conducted to investigate things that impact the TATO ratio on banks in Nigeria. Research results show that financial performance, management quality, company size, and economic growth influence the TATO ratio in banks in Nigeria (Susanto, 2015) . Third, several studies have also tried to develop a more comprehensive bank performance measurement model by considering the TATO ratio in Taiwan to develop a bank performance measurement model consisting of 11 financial ratios, including the TATO ratio, to measure bank financial efficiency and performance. The research results show that the developed bank performance measurement model is able to provide more accurate results in evaluating bank performance than traditional bank performance measurement models which only use a few financial ratios. So, research on the use of the TATO ratio in banks is always increasing and becoming more specific. This research is important to help banks understand their financial performance and increase the efficiency of asset use in generating income. However, this research must also be considered in a

broader context and used together with other financial ratios to obtain a very comprehensive perception of a bank's performance (Nur'aidawati, 2018) .

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding TATO in Islamic and conventional banking by using: (1) VOSviewer bibliographic research to analyze and study maps of document development in publications in the scientific field by creating metadata network maps; and (2) Library Research studies to analyze, identify and review articles from the nationally recognized journal Sinta. The implication and contribution of this research is to map research topics surrounding the TATO ratio in Islamic and conventional banks which are often or rarely studied by researchers so that they can become a reference for future researchers.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Total Asset Turnover (TATO) is the ratio used to estimate the effectiveness of the application of bank assets in generating income. TATO calculates the amount of bank income as a percentage of the total assets owned by the bank. In the banking context, TATO measures how effective it is banks use their assets to generate income, and the higher the TATO ratio, the more effective it is banking in generating income from the assets it owns (Yeye & Susilowati, 2017) . TATO can be generated by dividing total banking income together with the total amount of assets owned by the bank in a certain period of time. For example, if a bank has revenues of 1 billion dollars and total assets of 10 billion dollars, then the TATO is 0.1 or 10%. This means that per bank an generates 10 cents of income for every dollar of assets it owns. The higher the TATO ratio, the more efficient the bank is in generating income from the assets it owns (Jaryono & Mabchut, 2013) .

Bibliometric studies are a research approach that produces bibliographic and statistical data to analyze and evaluate the quantity and quality of literature published in a particular field. This method is usually used in studies about research developments, literature availability, or to evaluate the quality and impact of research. Bibliometric studies can be carried out using various types of bibliographic data, such as citation indexes, author indexes, and literature databases. In bibliometric studies, bibliographic data can be used to calculate the number of publications, citations, collaboration between authors, frequency of use of certain keywords, and various other indicators. Bibliometric studies can also be used to understand the development of a research field, track research trends, and identify the contribution of authors and research institutions to a field. In addition, this method can be used to evaluate the impact of research, estimate the value of a journal, or assess the quality of a research program or public policy (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is software used to analyze and visualize networks and clusters of bibliometric data. VOSviewer allows users to analyze and visualize important patterns in the literature related to a particular topic. In VOSviewer, users can enter bibliographic data from anywhere, such as PubMed, Web of Science, and Scopus. After entering bibliographic data, users can perform analyzes and visualize networks of various bibliometric elements, such as keywords, authors,

journals, and subjects. VOSviewer can be used to identify relationships between bibliometric elements, such as keywords that frequently appear together in a particular research topic, or authors who frequently collaborate in a particular research field. VOSviewer can be used to create interesting network visualizations, such as graphs showing relationships between keywords or authors. VOSviewer has been used widely in various research fields, including social sciences, medicine, and engineering, to analyze and visualize important patterns in literature related to a topic or research area (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

Library Research is a research method that aims to study and analyze documents related to a particular research topic. This method involves reviewing and evaluating various available sources of information such as books, scientific journals, government documents, or other sources of information related to the research topic. Library Research studies are usually carried out as an initial stage in conducting new research or as part of a larger study.. The aim is to understand the current status of knowledge and knowledge gaps that still need to be researched in a particular topic. In a Library Research study, researchers will search for and collect information relevant to the research topic. After that, the information will be collected and evaluated to identify trends, patterns, or findings that are relevant to the research topic. The results of this evaluation are then used to create a synthesis and conclusions on the information that has been collected. Library Research studies have several advantages, such as they can help speed up research by providing relevant information and can help identify research areas that still need further research. Library Research studies can also help to strengthen arguments and conclusions in research by providing support from relevant literature (El-Halaby et al., 2021) .

III. METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mixed approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric research and qualitative methods in document review research. The research object is Total Asset Turnover (TATO). The type of data used is secondary data. The range of data used is research articles regarding EPS in Islamic and conventional banks.

The source of data collection is searching for the nationally recognized Sinta magazine via the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) and software Perish/Harzing. Data analysis tools use Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop and VOSviewer software. Data collection techniques include: (1) open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for magazines based on the category of the title, including “ Total Asset Turnover ” and “ TATO ” for the entire year period; (2) collect journal name data in Microsoft Excel and identify duplicate journal names; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information System) and PDF (Portable Document) formats Format) from all journals where data was collected; and (4) entering the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) map the distribution of journal publications related to TATO using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop based

on publication year; (2) mapping the results of bibliographic network visualization and journal publishing trends around TATO using the VOSviewer (Visualizing Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and entries; and (3) mapping research topics around TATO using a Library Research (Rohimah et al., 2023) .

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping Distribution of Scientific Publications regarding Total Asset Turnover (TATO) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

There are 339 national Sinta journals based on data collection results using Microsoft Excel and Mendeley Desktop from the Garuda website (Garba Digital Reference) and software Perish/Harzing over the period 2012 to 2023. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Journal publication data about TATO by year

Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications	Year	Number of Publications
2012	1	2016	19	2020	45
2013	4	2017	23	2021	55
2014	12	2018	22	2022	87
2015	16	2019	44	2023	11

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

VOSviewer Bibliometric Study Mapping of Total Asset Turnover (TATO) in Islamic and Conventional Banking

Article search results in the Perish/Harzing software are exported in RIS (Research Information System) was then imported and analyzed using VOSviewer software. The following results:

Figure 1. Network visualization of a map of research developments around TATO.

Source: Processed data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

VOSviewer software visualization results on a research development map related to TATO in Islamic and conventional banks, there are 5 clusters and 104 thematic components on the map, including:

- Cluster 1 consists of 47 topic items, namely: capital, capital structure, classical assumption test, coefficient, company, criteria, data analysis method/technique, data collection technique, determination, documentation technique, f test, factor, financial report/statement, firm size, idx, increase, independent variable, influence, inventory turnover, profit, manufacturing company, multiple linear regression, net profit margin, npm, partial test, population, profit growth, profitability, property, purposive sampling technique, quantitative approach/research, r square, research method/sample, sales growth, sampling method, significant effect/influence, stock exchange, t test, test result, total assets.
- Cluster 2 consists of 28 topic items, namely: bei, Indonesian stock exchange, current ratio, panel data, debt, der, equity ratio, classic, Microsoft Excel, influence of current ratio/debt/return, company, price earning ratio, purposive sampling, return, roa, roe, significant to return, social science, spss, tattoo, tbk, total asset turnover.
- Cluster 3 consists of 17 topic items, namely: data analysis, financial performance, hypothesis testing, Indonesian stock exchange, investment, investor, multiple linear regression, performance, positive effect, price, purposive sampling method, ratio, significant negative/positive effect, stock price/return, tat.

- Cluster 4 consists of 5 topic items, namely: earnings, earnings per share, Indonesian effects, eps, share.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research around the Influence of Ratios Total Asset Turnover (TATO) in Banking Islamic and Conventional

Library Research study in previous research journals, researchers found 26 influences of TATO on Islamic and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, stock beta (Mutmainah, 2019) . TATO and stock beta are two different concepts and have different influences on banking performance. TATO measures how effectively a company uses its assets to generate income, while stock beta measures the systematic risk or market risk associated with a company's shares. In a banking context, TATO can influence stock beta. The higher the TATO of a bank, the higher the level of risk that the bank may face. This is due to the fact that the higher the TATO, the greater the amount of assets traded and the greater the risk associated with market fluctuations. However, the influence of TATO on banking stock beta cannot be ascertained directly, because there are many other factors that influence stock beta, such as company size, financial leverage, and the company's business risk profile. Therefore, the influence of TATO on stock beta must be analyzed holistically by considering all relevant factors. In order to minimize risk and improve banking performance, management needs to pay attention to both TATO and stock beta. Banks that are efficient in managing their assets and have a good risk profile can show better performance and have lower stock betas, so they can attract investor interest and increase the value of their shares in the market.

Second, Debt to Equity Ratio /DER (Yuliana, 2021) . TATO and DER are both important financial ratios for analyzing the financial condition of companies, especially banks. TATO measures a company's efficiency in generating income from its assets, while DER measures the amount of debt a company uses to finance its assets compared to its equity. The impact of TATO on DER in the banking sector may vary depending on the specific situation. In general, the higher the TATO of a bank, the lower the DER, because the more effective a bank is in generating income from its assets, the less debt is needed to finance those assets. However, keep in mind that TATO that is too high can also pose higher risks, such as higher credit and liquidity risks. Conversely, the lower the banking TATO, the higher the DER, because banks have to rely on more debt to finance their less productive assets. However, if the DER is too high, banks can face higher risks in managing their debt, such as interest risk and bankruptcy risk. In banking financial analysis, it is important to consider these two ratios simultaneously and in the context of the situation and conditions that apply to the company.

Third, Dividend Payout Ratio /DPR (admin, 2016) . TATO and DPR are two important metrics in banking and financial analysis. TATO is a ratio that measures a company's efficiency in generating income from its assets, while DPR measures how much of its profits are distributed as dividends to shareholders. The impact

of TATO on DPR on the banking sector can vary depending on the specific situation and conditions of each bank. However, in general, high TATO can lead to higher DPR as well. When TATO increases, it means that the bank is successful in generating more income from each asset. This shows that the bank is more efficient in utilizing its assets to generate income. If the bank has sufficient profits to distribute dividends, they may be inclined to increase the DPR, as their efficiency in generating income from assets provides room for risk taking in profit distribution. However, there are a number of other factors that may influence the relationship between TATO and DPR in the banking sector. For example, if banks experience a decline in overall financial performance, their DPR may fall even if their TATO increases. Apart from that, company policies, investment plans, and capital requirements can also influence the relationship between TATO and DPR in banking. In short, TATO and DPR are two important measures in banking and financial analysis and they depend on each other. However, the impact of TATO on DPR for the banking sector can vary depending on the specific situation and conditions of each bank.

Fourth, Dividend Yield (Prakoso Mochammad, 2016) . TATO and Dividend Yield are two different concepts in financial analysis. TATO measures how effectively a company generates income using the assets it owns, while dividend yield measures the profits the company provides to shareholders in the form of dividends. The effect of TATO on dividend yields in the banking industry cannot be determined directly because the two concepts are different. However, TATO can indirectly influence dividend yields through several factors, including: (1) Profitability: The higher the TATO, the more effectively the company uses its assets to generate income. This can increase company profits which in turn can affect dividend yields. (2) Distribution rate: Payout ratio is the ratio between the dividends paid by a company and its net profit. The higher the TATO, the more likely the company is to earn sufficient profits to pay dividends, thereby increasing the payout ratio and dividend yield. (3) Company growth: High TATO can indicate good growth in the company. This can help companies increase investor confidence and attract more capital for investment. In the long term, this can increase the company's Dividend Yield. Overall, although there is no direct relationship between TATO and Dividend Yield in banking, TATO can influence Dividend Yield indirectly through several factors such as profitability, payout ratio, and company growth.

Fifth, Expected Return (Aprisilya Wisnu, 2016) . The higher the TATO ratio, the more effectively a company uses its assets to generate income. The influence of TATO on Expected Returns in banking can be explained as follows: (1) Business Risk: The higher the TATO, the higher the company's business risk. It's true, companies that effectively use their assets to generate greater revenues also face higher business risks. On the other hand, companies with low TATO will have lower business risks. (2) Financial Leverage: The higher the TATO, the higher the company's financial leverage. Financial leverage refers to the use of debt to finance a company's assets. In the banking industry, financial leverage can increase a company's risk. If the company experiences a loss, the company's debts still have

to be paid and this can cause a decrease in the value of the company's shares. (3) Operational Efficiency: High TATO can increase the company's operational efficiency. The more efficiently a company uses its assets to generate income, the lower the company's operational costs and the greater the profits generated. This can increase the company's Expected Return. In the banking context, high TATO can increase a company's Expected Return if business risks and financial leverage can be controlled well and the company's operational efficiency can increase revenue. However, it should be remembered that the influence of TATO on expected returns in banking cannot be viewed in isolation and must be considered together with other factors such as market conditions, regulations and risk management.

Sixth, Earning Per Share /EPS (Hermansyah, 2019) . In the banking industry, TATO can affect EPS. The higher the TATO ratio, the more effectively the bank uses its assets to generate income. In the long term, this can increase EPS because the bank can generate more profits from the assets it owns. However, TATO's impact on EPS can also be influenced by other factors, such as operational costs and interest rates. If operational costs are high, even though TATO is high, the resulting net profit can decrease and have an impact on EPS. Likewise, if interest rates rise, this can affect bank profit margins and in turn, can affect EPS. In conclusion, TATO can have a positive effect on EPS in banking, but other factors must also be considered in evaluating a bank's overall financial performance.

Seventh, Financial Distress (nursidin, 2021) . The higher the TATO ratio, the more effectively the company manages assets and generates income. However, the impact of TATO on financial difficulties in the banking sector can vary depending on other factors that influence a company's finances. In general, the higher the TATO, the lower the likelihood of financial difficulties in the business. This is due to how efficiently the company uses its assets so that it can generate sufficient income to cover operational costs and pay debts. In the banking context, a high TATO can also indicate that the bank is able to obtain sufficient income from its operational activities such as providing loans, so that it is able to maintain liquidity and reduce the risk of Financial Distress. However, a TATO that is too high can also pose a risk of Financial Distress in banking. This happens if the company takes too big a risk in obtaining income, such as providing high-risk loans and inadequate risk management. If the loan experiences problems, the bank will have difficulty paying its obligations and will be exposed to financial risks Distress. Therefore, TATO is an important factor in determining the risk of Financial Distress in banking. However, other factors such as risk management, asset quality and liquidity also need to be considered to reduce the risk of Financial Distress.

Eighth, Gross Profit Margin /GPM (Ilham, 2020) . In the banking industry, TATO can affect GPM. The higher the TATO, the more assets are used to generate sales, so the company can achieve greater economies of scale. In this case, companies can reduce production costs and increase operational efficiency. This can lead to an increase in the company's gross profit and, ultimately, increase GPM. However, TATO can also have a negative impact on GPM. If a business uses too many assets to generate revenue, operating costs can increase significantly. As a result, even though sales increase, gross profit may decrease, and GPM may also

decrease. Therefore, it is important for banking companies to pay attention to their TATO and GPM ratios and ensure that they use their assets in an efficient manner to achieve optimal gross profits and improve their overall financial performance.

Ninth, share prices (Hasanah, 2021) . The impact of TATO on banking sector share prices can vary depending on market and industry conditions. However, in general, the higher the TATO of a banking company, the greater the possibility that its share price will increase. This is caused by several factors. First, banking companies that are efficient in generating income from their assets will tend to experience faster and more stable growth, which in turn can increase investor confidence and encourage share prices to rise. Second, the more efficient a company is in using its assets, the higher the possibility that the company will have greater profits. This can improve a company's financial performance and provide a positive signal to the market, which can also have a positive impact on share prices. However, it should be noted that TATO is not the only factor that influences banking company share prices. There are other factors such as overall stock market conditions, interest rates, government policies, and internal company factors that can also impact stock prices. Therefore, TATO must be seen as one of the factors that can influence banking company share prices, and not as the only determining factor.

Tenth, dividend policy (admin, 2016) . In the banking context, TATO can influence dividend policy in two main ways: (1) A high TATO can explain that the bank can create higher income with the assets it owns. This can increase shareholder confidence in the bank and encourage the bank to distribute larger dividends in the distribution of profits generated. (2) However, a low TATO may indicate that the bank is having difficulty creating adequate income to support its business with the assets it owns. This can make banks more careful in paying dividends and choose to retain a portion of their net profits to strengthen capital and maintain financial health. Thus, it can be concluded that the influence of TATO on dividend policy in banking varies depending on the size of the TATO ratio. However, it is important to remember that dividend policy is not only influenced by internal factors such as the TATO ratio, but also by external factors such as market conditions and regulations.

Eleventh, investment decisions (Mutmainah, 2019) . The influence of TATO on investment decisions in banking can vary depending on market conditions and the banking industry as a whole. However, in general, TATO can provide important explanations for investors in assessing a company's efficiency and growth potential, namely: (1) TATO can provide an indication of how well the company is utilizing its assets to generate income. In the banking industry, where assets are in the form of money and securities, a high TATO can indicate a company's ability to generate stable and increasing income from its asset portfolio. (2) TATO can also help investors compare the company's efficiency with its competitors in the same industry. If a company has a higher TATO than its competitors, this can indicate a competitive advantage and the ability to attract customers by offering better services and products. However, TATO should not be the main thing in investment decisions. There are many other things to consider, such as credit risk, economic growth, and regulatory policies. Therefore, before making investment decisions in

banking, investors must carry out an in-depth analysis of the company's overall financial performance and market conditions.

Twelfth, financial performance (Yuliana, 2021) . In the banking context, TATO measures how efficiently a bank uses its assets to create income. The higher the TATO ratio, the more effective the bank is in increasing income from the assets it owns. The influence of TATO on financial performance in banking is positive. This is because the more effective a bank is in using its assets to create income, the higher the bank's possibility of creating high profits. Thus, banks that have a high TATO ratio tend to have better financial performance compared to banks that have a low TATO ratio. Apart from that, the TATO ratio can also support banks in analyzing potential problems related to inefficient use of assets. If the TATO ratio is low, this can indicate that the bank may have assets that are unproductive or not used optimally, so the bank can take corrective action to increase the efficiency of asset use. However, there is something that needs to be noted that the TATO ratio cannot be used as a priority in measuring financial performance in banking. There are many other factors that also influence financial performance in banking, such as credit risk, operational costs, and changes in regulations. Therefore, the TATO ratio must be seen in the context of the overall financial performance of banks.

Thirteenth, company performance (admin, 2016) . In the banking industry, TATO can be calculated by dividing operating income by the total assets owned by the bank. The influence of TATO on company performance in banking can be seen from several aspects, including: (1) Profitability: The higher the TATO of a bank, the more effective the bank is in using its assets to create income. This can increase bank profitability, especially if operational costs can be controlled well. However, if TATO is too high, the bank may lack liquidity because assets are turned over too quickly. (2) Growth: A high TATO can also be an indication that the bank has the ability to obtain funds from the market and utilize them efficiently to increase its business growth. (3) Risk: A TATO that is too high can also pose a risk for the bank, especially if the bank is too focused on turning over assets to generate income without paying attention to the risks faced. Risks that may occur include credit, liquidity and market risks.

Fourteenth, company value (Prakoso Mochammad, 2016) . In the banking context, TATO can be understood as how effective the bank is in generating income from its assets such as loans, investments, etc. The influence of TATO on company value in the banking industry can be explained as follows: (1) An increase in TATO tends to increase bank profitability, because banks are able to create multiple income from every dollar of assets owned. Increased profitability can ultimately increase company value. (2) TATO that is too high can also indicate higher risk because banks may be too aggressive in providing loans and investing. If this risk occurs, the bank may experience losses which can reduce the value of the company. Apart from that, company value is also influenced by other factors such as management quality, market conditions and applicable regulations. Therefore, TATO itself cannot be used as the sole benchmark in determining company value. Overall, TATO can have a positive effect on company value in the banking industry if banks can maintain a good level of profitability and manage risk well. However,

TATO is not the only factor that influences company value and needs to be considered in a broader context.

Fifteenth, changes in profit (Aprisilya Wisnu, 2016) . In the banking industry, TATO measures how well a bank uses its assets to generate income. The effect of TATO on changes in banking profits can be explained as follows: (1) High TATO can increase net profit. If a bank can create greater income from the assets it owns, then the bank can earn greater profits. This happens because banks can optimize the use of their assets to generate income. (2) Low TATO can reduce net profit. If the bank cannot create sufficient returns from the assets it owns, the bank will experience a decline in profits. This happens because banks are unable to maximize the use of their assets and are unable to create adequate income to cover operational costs. (3) Stable TATO can help maintain profits. If the bank can maintain a stable TATO, then the bank can maintain a consistent level of income from the assets it owns. This can help banks maintain consistent profits over time. In conclusion, TATO has a significant influence on changes in banking profits. Therefore, banks must pay attention to TATO and optimize the use of their assets to increase efficiency and increase revenue so as to increase net profit.

Sixteenth, profit growth (Hermansyah, 2019) . The influence of TATO on profit growth in banking institutions varies depending on other factors that influence banking performance. However, in general, banks with high TATO are more likely to achieve better profit growth than banks with low TATO. This is caused by several factors, namely: (1) Banks with high TATO are able to generate higher income with the same or fewer assets than banks with low TATO. In this case, banks with high TATO tend to produce lower operational costs and are more efficient in managing their assets. (2) Banks with high TATO are also more likely to have lower risk because they have fewer assets. This can reduce risk costs and increase profitability. However, there are several other aspects that can impact the relationship between TATO and profit growth, such as interest rates, inflation and market risk. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a more in-depth analysis to determine the relationship between TATO and profit growth in banking specifically.

Seventeenth, income growth (nursidin, 2021) . In banking, TATO measures how effectively a bank uses its assets (such as cash, securities, credit) to generate income. The effect of TATO on banking income growth can be described as follows: (1) the level of TATO can increase banking income growth. With better efficiency in asset use, banks can collect more income from the assets they own. This can increase overall bank revenue growth. (2) Low TATO can slow down banking revenue growth. If the bank is not effective in using its assets to generate income, the income generated will be low. This can affect the bank's overall revenue growth. Therefore, TATO can have a significant impact on banking revenue growth. Banks that are effective in using their assets will tend to have higher TATO and better income growth. Meanwhile, banks that are ineffective in using their assets will tend to have lower TATO and slower income growth.

Eighteenth, giving a Going Concern Opinion (Ilham, 2020) . In the banking context, TATO can influence the giving of a going concern opinion because of its relationship to the bank's ability to generate sufficient income to repay its financial obligations in the future. If TATO is low, it means that the bank is not efficient in

generating income from all the assets it owns, so the possibility of the bank experiencing financial difficulties and having difficulty paying back its financial obligations in the future is greater. In this case, the auditor can provide a negative going concern opinion if he sees the possibility of the bank experiencing financial difficulties and difficulty surviving in the future due to low TATO. However, a negative going concern opinion is not only based on one financial ratio, but must be considered with other relevant factors in assessing the bank's overall financial condition. In practice, auditors will look not only at TATO, but also at other factors such as liquidity, solvency and profitability in assessing the bank's overall financial condition and providing an objective and appropriate going concern opinion.

Nineteenth, Price to Book Value /PBV (Hasanah, 2021) . Total Asset Turnover (TATO) and Price to Book Value (PBV) are both ratios used to measure the financial performance of a company, such as banking companies. TATO measures the effectiveness of a company using its assets to collect revenue, while PBV measures the market value of a company compared to the value of its assets on the books. The effect of TATO on PBV in banking can vary depending on factors that influence the company's financial performance, such as company size, markets served, and the overall business environment. In general, the higher the TATO of a banking company, the more efficient the company is in generating income from the assets it owns. This can indicate the potential for greater profits and better performance, which can positively influence PBV. However, the effect of TATO on PBV can be influenced by other factors, such as interest rates, market risks and overall economic conditions. For example, if interest rates rise significantly, this can negatively affect the financial performance of a banking company and reduce its PBV, even though its TATO is high. In addition, larger banking companies may have higher PBV even though their TATO is lower compared to smaller banking companies. This could be due to investors' greater trust in banking companies, which could influence their PBV positively. In conclusion, TATO can influence PBV in banking companies positively if the company is efficient in generating income from the assets it owns. However, the effect of TATO on PBV can be influenced by other factors such as interest rates, market risk and company size.

Twentieth, Price Earning Ratio /PER (admin, 2016) . TATO and PER are two different financial ratios in fundamental analysis. TATO measures how efficiently a bank uses its assets to generate income, while PER measures a company's relative valuation by comparing the company's share price with its net profit per share. The effect of TATO on PER in banking can vary depending on certain factors, such as the type and size of bank, market conditions, and other factors. However, in general, if a bank has a high TATO, this indicates that the bank is more efficient at generating income from its assets, which can result in higher profits. This can make investors more interested in buying the bank's shares, which can increase the share price and therefore, increase the PER. However, it is important to remember that the effect of TATO on PER is not always linear and can depend on many other factors, such as market risk, competition, and economic factors. Therefore, it is important to conduct a thorough analysis and use other financial

ratios as part of a more comprehensive fundamental analysis before making an investment decision.

Twenty-first, Return On Assets /ROA (Mutmainah, 2019) . The effect of TATO on ROA in banking can be explained as follows: (1) High TATO can increase ROA. With a high TATO, a company can generate higher income from the assets it owns, which in turn can increase ROA. In this case, banks can increase their operational efficiency by using their assets more effectively. (2) However, TATO that is too high can also reduce ROA. If a company focuses too much on increasing revenue at the expense of profitability, this can reduce ROA. In terms of banking, if you focus too much on increasing the volume of loans or investments, the risks taken can increase and reduce the company's profitability. (3) ROA can also influence TATO. If the company generates high profits from its assets, this can increase TATO. Conversely, if ROA is low, this can reduce TATO because the company is not effective in generating income from the assets it owns. (4) Finally, it should be noted that the effect of TATO on ROA can vary for each company, depending on different economic conditions and industries. Therefore, TATO and ROA measurements must be analyzed in more depth to understand their influence precisely. Overall, TATO can influence ROA in banking, but the relationship between the two is not simple and needs to be analyzed in more depth to understand its influence precisely.

Twenty-second, Return On Equity /ROE (Yuliana, 2021) . TATO and ROE are two financial ratios that are often used to measure a company's financial performance. TATO measures how efficient the company is in using its assets to generate sales, while ROE measures how effective the company is in generating profits from its equity. In banking, TATO can significantly influence ROE. The higher the TATO, the more efficient the bank is in using its assets to generate income. This can increase ROE, because the bank can generate greater profits from the equity available for investment. However, TATO's influence on ROE is also influenced by other aspects such as interest rates, market competition and credit risk. For example, a bank that has a high TATO but also has a high credit risk may not produce a high ROE, because the profits generated will most likely be used to cover losses due to credit risk. In practice, banks must seek an optimal balance between TATO and ROE, taking into account various factors that influence their financial performance. This can be done by increasing efficiency in asset use, minimizing credit risk, and optimizing capital allocation to maximize return on equity.

Twenty-third, Return On Investment /ROI (admin, 2016) . In the banking industry, TATO can influence ROI in several ways: (1) Efficiency of asset use: The higher a bank's TATO, the more efficiently the bank uses its assets to make a profit. This can help banks to increase ROI by generating more income from owned assets. (2) Credit quality: TATO can also affect the credit quality of a bank. Banks that have a high TATO always have a higher quality credit portfolio because they only provide credit to borrowers who they feel have the ability to repay. Higher quality credit tends to have a higher rate of return, which can increase ROI. (3) Competition: TATO can also affect competition among banks. Banks that have a high TATO can lower their operational costs and offer lower interest rates to attract

customers. This can increase the bank's customer base and ultimately increase ROI. In order to increase ROI, banks can increase TATO by increasing the efficiency of asset use, improving credit quality, and reducing operational costs. However, it is important to remember that a balance between high TATO and good credit quality must be maintained so that banks can maintain a good rate of return in the long term.

Twenty-fourth, stock returns (Prakoso Mochammad, 2016) . The effect of TATO on stock returns in banks can vary, depending on various factors such as the industrial sector, economic conditions and internal factors of the bank itself. However, in general, a high TATO can increase banking stock returns because it can indicate that the bank is able to generate higher income from every dollar of assets it owns. This shows that a high TATO can indicate that the bank is able to manage its assets well and efficiently, so that it can generate higher income. This situation can increase investor confidence and encourage share prices to rise. However, keep in mind that a TATO that is too high can also indicate that the bank is taking too much risk to increase its income. Risks that are too large can result in significant losses and reduce banking performance. Therefore, it is necessary to maintain a balance between high TATO and controlled risks to ensure healthy and sustainable banking performance.

Twenty-fifth, underpricing of shares (Aprisilya Wisnu, 2016) . In the banking industry, TATO can influence stock underpricing in several ways. First, the higher the TATO, the higher the company's ability to generate income from the assets it owns. This can provide a positive signal to potential investors that the company is performing well, thereby reducing the level of underpricing of shares when the company is listed on the stock market. Second, the higher the TATO, the lower the business risk faced by the company. Low risk can attract investor interest, thereby reducing stock underpricing. However, on the other hand, companies with low TATO may be considered to have higher business risks. This can increase the level of underpricing of shares when the company is listed on the stock market. Apart from that, underwriting banking shares is dependent on several other factors, for example on financial performance, company size, market conditions, and so on. Thus, there needs to be a deeper study to identify the influence of TATO on underpricing of shares in banking.

Twenty-sixth, capital structure (Hermansyah, 2019) . The influence of TATO on the capital structure of banks can vary depending on company policies and strategies. However, in general, banks that have a high TATO will tend to have a lower capital structure, which means they use more equity funds than debt to finance their assets. This can happen because banks that are efficient in using their assets to generate income will tend to find it easier to obtain equity financing, and at the same time, can reduce dependence on debt which can have an impact on the company's financial risk. However, it is important to note that corporate policies and strategies can influence the relationship between TATO and capital structure. For example, banking companies that want to grow their business quickly may choose to use more debt to finance their growth, even if their TATO is high. Therefore, in observing the relationship between TATO and capital structure in banking companies, it is important to consider several other factors such as

interest rates, market risk, and company policies regarding financing and financial risk management.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows: First, based on a diagram of the number of research publications related to the determinants and influence of total asset turnover (TATO) in Islamic and conventional banks in the period 2012 to 2023, taken from the nationally recognized Sinta magazine, there are 339 articles published. Second, based on the VOSviewer bibliometric study map, the network visualization results related to TATO rates on Islamic and conventional banks are divided into 5 groups and 104 thematic categories. Cluster 1 had 47 subjects, cluster 2 had 28 subjects, cluster 3 had 17 subjects, and cluster 4 had 5 subjects. Third, based on a Library Research mapping study, there are 26 impacts of TATO on Islamic and conventional banks, namely: share beta, Debt to Equity Ratio /DER, Dividend Payout Ratio /DPR, Dividend Yield, Expected Return, Earning Per Share /EPS, Financial Distress, Gross Profit Margin /GPM, stock prices, dividend policy, investment decisions, financial performance, company performance, company value, changes in profits, profit growth, income growth, giving a Going Concern Opinion, Price to Book Value /PBV, Price Earning Ratio / PER, Return On Assets /ROA, Return On Equity /ROE, Return On Investment /ROI, stock returns, stock underpricing, and capital structure.

Suggestion

It is recommended that future research use a wider data sample, both from national accredited journals Sinta and international journals indexed by Scopus, to be able to explain a broader research scheme, considering the limited data sample in this study and the possibility of adding larger studies. The time frame for the research data may be. The following research results were obtained: First, the mapping results are expected to show a higher and broader degree of generalization. Second, the results of the Library Research can be interpreted in a more complex way.

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